

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 143

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 143

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 143:1 Hear my prayer, O LORD, "Give ear to my supplications! Answer me in Your ^bfaithfulness, in Your ^crighteousness! ² And ^ado not enter into judgment with Your servant, For in Your sight ^bno man living is righteous. ³ For the enemy has persecuted my soul; He has crushed my life ^ato the ground; He ^bhas made me dwell in dark places, like those who have long been dead. ⁴ Therefore ^amy spirit ¹is overwhelmed within me; My heart is ^{2b}appalled within me.</p>	<p>Psa. 143:1 מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד יְהוָה אֱשָׁמַע תְּפִלָּתִי הָאֲזִינָה אֶל־תַּחֲנוּנֵי בְּאִמְנוֹתֶךָ עֲנֵנִי בְּצַדִּיקְתֶּךָ : ² וְאַל־תִּבְוֹא בְּמִשְׁפַּט אֶת־עַבְדְּךָ כִּי לֹא־יִצְדַק לִפְנֶיךָ כָּל־חַי : ³ כִּי רִדְךָ אוֹיֵב אֲנַפְשִׁי דַכָּא לְאַרְץ חַיְתִּי הוֹשִׁיבֵנִי בְּמַחְשָׁפִים כְּמַתִּי עוֹלָם : ⁴ וַתִּתְעַטֶּף עָלַי רוּחִי בְּתוֹכִי יִשְׁתַּוְּמֵם לִבִּי : ⁵ וְצָכַרְתִּי יָמִים אֶמְקָרֵם הִגִּיתִי בְּכָל־פְּעֻלָּךְ בְּמַעֲשֵׂה יְדֶיךָ אֲשׁוּחַח : ⁶ כַּרְשִׁיתִי יְדֵי אֱלֹהִים נַפְשִׁי אֶכְאַרְץ־עֵינֶיךָ לְךָ סִלָּה : ⁷ מִתַּחַר עֲנֵנִי וַיְהִי כְּלָתָה רוּחִי אֶל־ תִּסְתַּר פְּנֵיךָ מִמֶּנִּי וְנִמְשַׁלְתִּי עִם־יָרְדֵי בּוֹר : ⁸ הִשְׁמִיעֵנִי בִּבְקָר אֶתְסַדֶּךָ כִּי־בָהּ בָטַחְתִּי הוֹדִיעֵנִי יְהוָה אֱלֹהִים כִּי־אֱלֹהִים נִשְׁאַתִּי נַפְשִׁי : ⁹ תִּצְוֵלֵנִי מֵאֹיְבֵי וַיְהִי אֱלֹהִים כֶּסֶתִי : ¹⁰ לְמַדְנִי אֶלְעֲשׂוֹת רְצוֹנֶךָ כִּי־אַתָּה אֱלֹהִים רוּחֶךָ טוֹבָה תִּגְדַּלֵנִי בְּאַרְץ מִישׁוֹר : ¹¹ לְמַעַן־ שְׁמֹךָ יִהְיֶה תִתְנַנֵּן בְּצַדִּיקְתֶּךָ אֲתוֹצִיא מִצָּרָה נַפְשִׁי : ¹² וְבַחֲסִדְּךָ תִצְמַחֵת אֵיבֵי וַהֲאֵבַדְתָּ כָּל־צָרָרֵי נַפְשִׁי כִּי אֲנִי עַבְדְּךָ :</p>
<p>Psa. 143:5 I ^aremember the days of old; I ^bmeditate on all Your doings; I ^cmuse on the work of Your hands. ⁶ I ^astretch out my hands to You; My ^bsoul <i>longs</i> for You, as a ¹parched land. ²Selah.</p>	
<p>Psa. 143:7 ^aAnswer me quickly, O LORD, my ^bspirit fails; "Do not hide Your face from me, Or I will become like ^athose who go down to the pit. ⁸ Let me hear Your ^alovingkindness ^bin the morning; For I trust ^cin You;</p>	

Teach me the ^dway in which I
should walk;

For to You I ^elift up my soul.

⁹ ^aDeliver me, O LORD, from my
enemies;

¹I take refuge in You.

Psa. 143:10 ^aTeach me to do
Your will,

For You are my God;

Let ^bYour good Spirit ^elead me on
level ¹ground.

¹¹ ^aFor the sake of Your name, O
LORD, ^brevive me.

^eIn Your righteousness bring my
soul out of trouble.

¹² And in Your lovingkindness, ^{1a}cut
off my enemies

And ^bdestroy all those who afflict
my soul,

For ^eI am Your servant.

References

Psalm 143:1

^aPs 140:6

^bPs 89:1, 2

Ps 71:2

Psalm 143:2

^aJob 14:3; 22:4

^b1 Kin 8:46; Job 4:17; 9:2; 25:4; Ps 130:3; Eccl 7:20; Rom 3:10, 20; Gal 2:16

Psalm 143:3

^aPs 44:25

^bPs 88:6; Lam 3:6

Psalm 143:4

¹Lit *faints*

²Or *desolate*

^aPs 77:3; 142:3

^bLam 3:11

Psalm 143:5

^aPs 77:5, 10, 11

^bPs 77:12

Ps 105:2

Psalm 143:6

¹Lit *weary*

²*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aJob 11:13; Ps 88:9

^bPs 42:2; 63:1

Psalm 143:7

^aPs 69:17

^bPs 73:26; 84:2; Jer 8:18; Lam 1:22

Ps 27:9; 69:17; 102:2

^aPs 28:1; 88:4

Psalm 143:8

^aPs 90:14

^bPs 46:5

Ps 25:2

^aPs 27:11; 32:8; 86:11

Ps 25:1; 86:4

Psalm 143:9

¹Lit *To You have I bidden*

^aPs 31:15; 59:1

Psalm 143:10

¹Lit *land*

^aPs 25:4, 5; 119:12

^bNeh 9:20

Ps 23:3

Psalm 143:11

^aPs 25:11

^bPs 119:25

Ps 31:1; 71:2

Psalm 143:12

¹Or *silence*

^aPs 54:5

^bPs 52:5

Ps 116:16

Targum

Psa. 143:1 A praise for David. O LORD, hear my prayer, listen to my supplication; in your truth answer me, in your generosity. ² And do not enter the house of judgment with your servant, for nothing that lives will be pure in your presence. ³ For the enemy is persecuting my soul; he has crushed my life to the earth; he made me dwell in darkness like those who are dead in this age. ⁴ When my soul grows weary against me, in my body my heart will be confounded. ⁵ I called to mind the days of old; I meditated on all your deeds; I will speak of the works of your hands. ⁶ I spread out my hands in prayer before you; my soul looks towards you forever like a land that is thirsty for water. ⁷ Hurry, answer me, O LORD; my spirit yearned for you; do not remove your presence from me; and I have become like those who descend to the pit of the grave. ⁸ Proclaim your goodness to me in the morning, for I have hoped in your word; make me know this way that I walk, for to you have I lifted up my soul in prayer. ⁹ Deliver me from my enemies, O LORD; I have reckoned your word to be redeeming. ¹⁰ Teach me to do your will, for you are my God; your good holy spirit will guide me in the land correctly. ¹¹ For the sake of your name, O LORD, sustain me; by your righteousness bring my soul out of distress. ¹² And by your kindness overthrow my enemies, and destroy all those who oppress my soul, for I am your servant. --

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm is a continuation of Psalm 142.

Notes on this Psalm

Throughout the Psalm David calls upon the Sefirah Chesed for the LORD's lovingkindness.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

